

Travelling Motifs: Transmission and Transformation of the Bridge of Arta Tradition Across the Balkans

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Independent Research Paper

English adaptation of previous research conducted at Moscow State University

2026

Introduction

The present work is devoted to a topic little developed in Russian folklore studies, the Greek mythopoetic plot of the bridge of Arta, which goes back to the archetypal rite of the construction sacrifice, and the transformation of this plot across the Balkans.

The aim of the research is to analyse the Greek construction-sacrifice ballad (hereafter CSB) from the point of view of composition, to identify the specific motifs characteristic of the Greek ballad and the motifs characteristic of ballads current in other Balkan countries. This aim entails the following tasks:

- to select a body of texts from collections of folk songs on the basis of which the analysis will be carried out;
- to study the material and identify the structural features of each variant;
- to work out a general scheme according to which the composition of the CSB is built, and to apply to it the theory of V. Propp and A. Lord;
- to identify specific and common features in the structure of the Greek CSB by comparing it with other Balkan CSBs;
- to compile a catalogue of the motifs identified in the various CSBs.

The object of the research is a group of texts recorded from different singers across the Balkan peninsula. The main subject of the research is the plot of the Greek ballad of the bridge of Arta and its transformations across the Balkans.

The relevance of the work is determined by the need for a systematic description of the motifs of the Balkan construction-sacrifice ballads and for an analysis of the structural elements of the Greek ballad against the Balkan background. Of particular interest are the maps of the structural elements of the construction-sacrifice ballad compiled by the author of the present work. The Greek and other Balkan construction-sacrifice ballads also remain little studied in Russian scholarship. No major works devoted to the structure of the Greek construction-sacrifice ballad, or to any of its features, exist in Russia at present.

The scholarly novelty of the work lies in a fundamentally new approach to the study of the structure of the folk song with the help of the methods of V. Propp and A. Lord. The question of the two-part construction of the ballad has never been raised in the Greek tradition. The theory of V. Propp, well known in Russian scholarship, is applied here to folk songs taken from different regions of Greece. The attempt to map the elements of structure, the motifs of the construction-sacrifice ballad, on the material of folk songs is of importance. The attempt to compile a catalogue of Balkan motifs in Russian is also fundamentally new.

The theoretical significance of the work lies in the fact that, for the first time on the material of folk songs recorded in different countries of the Balkan peninsula, it examines the structure of the CSB and identifies the features characteristic of Greek ballads on the basis of new methods. The practical significance of the work lies in the possibility of using its materials to prepare a course of lectures and teaching aids in folklore studies, and for practical classes using the comparative method of literary studies. The results of the work may be used for compiling a catalogue of Balkan motifs of folk songs. The translations of texts carried out here for the first time may also be used both by compilers of collections of world folk songs and as auxiliary material when comparing the ballad of the bridge of Arta with similar ballads of other peoples.

Material of the Research

The work is built on the materials of already existing sources of Russian and foreign researchers, as well as on field research. The collections of folk songs recorded on the Balkan peninsula and beyond it that are used in this work are listed in the bibliography. The texts of the construction-sacrifice ballad current in the Balkans are known in many languages: Greek, Albanian, Romanian, Aromanian, Bulgarian, Macedonian, Serbian, Croatian, Bosnian, Turkish, Hungarian, Moldavian, as well as in Romani (Kalderash) and in the Pomak micro-language. In selecting the material we were guided by the following principles:

- The selection of texts is based on a linguo-geographic principle, that is, we selected and classified ballads current in one or another language rather than within the borders of a particular country (for example, a ballad recorded in Turkish on the territory of Greece is, in our understanding, a Turkish ballad). Thus, Greek ballads are those recorded in Greek not only on the Balkan peninsula but also beyond it (Pontus, Cappadocia, Cyprus and so on), and for this reason we include them in our work.
- It is assumed that Greek CSBs may have local differences in structure. In order to find this out, we selected Greek variants according to a geographical principle, choosing for analysis roughly the same number of texts from different regions of Greece: Epirus, Macedonia, Thrace, Thessaly, the Peloponnese, Central Greece, the Ionian Islands and Crete, Euboea, Cyprus, Cappadocia, Pontus.
- We examine the transformation of the plot of the bridge of Arta across the Balkans, and so from the other Balkan countries we chose the variants that differ most from the Greek ones and from one another, in order to show the diversity and specificity of the Balkan background and to bring out the structural features of the Greek ballad.
- According to the Parry-Lord theory, on which we rely, the notion of a fixed text is alien to the oral poet [Lord 1961: 1-231]. The singer holds in memory many unfixed models that must fit a definite rhythmic pattern. The singer never ceases to accumulate and rebuild formulas, thereby perfecting his art. He keeps in mind a definite set of themes and, following this scheme and using formulas, builds his song. The texts published in collections do not constitute a finished literary work; they only record an act of performance in a particular place, at a particular time, by a particular singer. On this basis, in order to extract the structure there is no need to analyse every song ever recorded, since each of them is unique, and only the motifs and formulas used by the singer remain unchanged.

Theoretical and Methodological Basis

The theoretical basis of this work is a wide range of studies on questions adjacent to our topic. Of great importance for us are the works of G. Megas [Megas 1976: 1-320], where 333 variants of the folk songs of the bridge of Arta are analysed; of I. Taloş [Taloş 1969: 22-56] and G. Vrabie [Vrabie 1966: 69-108], where the Romanian variants are examined in detail against the Balkan background; the article of K. Romaios [Ρωμάιος 1979: 19-42], which carries out a comparative analysis of Greek, Serbian and Bulgarian variants; the article of L. Parpulova [Parpulova 1983: 20-33], devoted to the structure and semantics of the Bulgarian CSB; the work of Z. Sako [Sako 1966: 155-165], where the Albanian ballads are analysed; and the collection of articles edited by A. Dundes [Dundes 1966: 1-214]. We also draw on the experience of Russian researchers who have studied the CSB: N. G. Golant [Golant 2009: 135-139], D. K. Zelenin [Zelenin 2004: 145-175], V. Vs. Ivanov [Ivanov 1997: 171-220].

The methodological basis is formed by the works of A. Lord, *The Singer of Tales* [Lord 1961: 1-231], and V. Ya. Propp, *Morphology of the Folktale* [Propp 1969: 1-132]. The motif catalogue of folk songs by B. Krstić [Krstić 1984: 59-66] was also used as a model. In the course of the work the structural-typological and the comparative methods of analysis were mainly applied. In compiling the maps of the motifs of the ballad we rely on the experience of N. I. Tolstoy in mapping the structural elements of the Polesian ballad of the daughter-in-law turned poplar [Tolstoy 1986: 39-43], and on the experience of M. M. Makartsev in mapping the motif of the smell coming from the brother, from another ballad also widespread in the Balkans, the ballad of the dead brother [Makartsev 2011: 321-327].

The Construction-Sacrifice Ballad in Russian and Foreign Scholarship. History of the Question

The main question that troubled researchers of the CSB over many years was the place where the ballad arose. For a century attempts continued to find on the Balkan peninsula the locus of the birth of the folk songs and the possible routes of their spread. At the very beginning researchers turned their attention to the Modern Greek sources. L. Saineanu, emphasising above all the Serbian and Romanian ballads because of their originality and beautiful poetic diction (which could be the result of a later creative reworking of the text), singled out on a number of grounds the Modern Greek versions as the primary source, from which, as he believed, the Albanian and Aromanian variants derive; the Hungarian versions, in his well-founded view, derive from Romanian sources [Saineanu 1969: 359-396]. A Greek primary source for the whole complex of Balkan CSB texts was assumed by G. Cocchiara [Cocchiara 1950: 38-81], P. Caraman [Caraman 1934: 64-102] and M. Arnaudov [Arnaudov 1920: 245-512].

Kostas Romaios carries out a comparative analysis of the Bulgarian, two Serbian and the Greek variants, and also examines separately the Romanian legend of Master Manole, and concludes that the song of the bridge of Arta is of Greek origin [Ρωμάιος 1979: 40].

J. Entwistle, in his work, investigated the Romanian song of Master Manole and found that the song is borrowed directly from Macedonia. However, Entwistle does not give weighty proof of his point of view. In the same work he writes that the primary variant of the song is the Greek variant from Cappadocia [Entwistle 1939: 511-529].

In the opinion of K. Schladebach, the Aromanian-Serbian variants are primary [Schladebach 1894: 79-121]. L. Saineanu points to the motif of Icarus in the Romanian variants as an indicator of the antiquity of the Romanian ballad [Saineanu 1902: 390-396]. M. Arnaudov, having compared 57 Bulgarian and 14 Greek versions of the ballad, fixes Epirus as the place of its origin [Arnaudov, *ibid.*: 500-512]. P. Skok holds that the ballad is of Aromanian origin [Skok 1929: 220-242]. S. Stefanović speaks of a polygenetic model of the origin of the ballad [Stefanović 1934: 188-210]. In 1962 I. Taloş published versions of carols from Transylvania in an archaic short form, which may be interpreted either as original forms or, on the contrary, as shortened forms of quiet-songs [Taloş 1962: 22-56]. M. Pop explains that the archetypal forms from southern Transylvania and the Banat, where a woman or a child is sacrificed, are primary, although he inclines toward a polygenetic explanation of the origin of the song [Pop 1963: 427-455]. G. Vrabie analyses 22 Greek, 42 Bulgarian, 5 Albanian, 5 Serbian and 55 Romanian songs (of these songs 15 are carols), and concludes that the Greek versions have the clearest sequence of motifs [Vrabie 1966: 108-144]. Z. Sako argues for the Albanian origin of the ballad, considering primary the version published in 1878 [Sako 1966: 21].

G. Megas rejects the theory of polygenesis, pointing out that only in the Greek songs is the type of building stable: in them a bridge is always and exclusively built, a complex architectural construction, and it is precisely in the building of a bridge that the probability of the building collapsing is high. Although the widespread occurrence of the construction-sacrifice rite increases the plausibility of a polygenetic origin, the coherence and clear sequence of motifs points rather to something else: the possibility of the ballad spreading through the builders' guilds of Epirus, who built most of the houses across the Ottoman empire and all the bridges over dangerous rivers after the seventeenth century [Megas 1976: 179].

M. Eliade locates the archaic motif of the construction sacrifice in the pre-Indo-European stratum of the cultural heritage of the Balkan region [Eliade 1982: 198]. The popularity and the striking similarity of the Balkan CSBs to the Indian ones, moreover, led many researchers to consider an Indian origin of the ballad. Asking how the ballad reached the Balkans from India, researchers were able to find an answer: it was carried by the Roma, wandering throughout the world. The theory of an Indian origin through the Roma was first put forward by F. H. Groome, who published a Romani ballad translated into English [Groome 2002: 12-13]. Thus the question of the place where the ballad was born remains open to this day.

Plot and Compositional Features of the Greek Construction-Sacrifice Ballad

Approaching the study of the ballad, we cannot but notice the two-dimensionality of its structure. On the one hand, reading the text of the ballad, we move from its beginning to its closing phase. On the other hand, in each of these parts we meet a definite number of components, heterogeneous in nature but inseparably connected with one another. Thus, in one dimension we deal with a sequence of scenes succeeding one another, the parts of the work that together make up the plot; in the other, with a multitude of jointly appearing heterogeneous components, the motifs.

The presence of two dimensions and at the same time the inner unity of construction set off the literary or folkloric work from the point of view of its structure. In this connection one may note the works in which the structure of works was studied: those of V. Ya. Propp (according to whose theory all fairy tales possess an unchanging structure, a composition consisting of 31 functions and a multitude of components linking them) and those of M. Parry and A. B. Lord (according to which the moment of creation of an epic song coincides with the moment of performance, the singer

building his song from a set of strictly defined themes). The correspondence of these two theories is noted by R. Alexander [Alexander 1995: 195-197]. Thus the first work is devoted to the structure of works, the second to the process of performance, but it has already been observed more than once that these two theories intersect at one point.

The structure of the Greek ballad fits the scheme proposed by G. Megas [Megas 1976: 21-23]. He derived this scheme by analysing 333 variants of the Greek ballad; his scheme includes nine episodes:

I. Exposition. II. The necessity of the sacrifice. III. The masters' agreement. IV. The summoning of the heroine. V. The scene with the ring. VI. The walling up. VII. The account of the fate of the sisters. VIII. The curse. IX. The ending.

Having studied the Balkan variants of the CSB, we arrive at the following scheme:

1. Exposition. Announcement of the problem.

In order to bring the listeners into the situation, the singer must show a certain initial situation. The exposition in the CSB is always expressed by a formula and necessarily contains the following information:

- the number of builders (and most often their names);
- an announcement of the problem: the building collapses;
- the type of building, its name and/or its geographical position (the last two features may be absent). Thus, in the Cypriot variants the place of building is designated by a long formula pointing to the connection of this place with the underworld (while no specific names are given):

Κάτω στους πέντε ποταμούς, κάτω στις πέντε βρύσες,
κάτω στις άκρες των ακρών εκεί που τελειώνει ο κόσμος,
κάτω στις άκρες των ακρών στη μέση του Μόου,
έκτιζαν γεφύρι και είπαν πως είναι του φόβου.
Γιοφύρι είναι που χτίζανε με δώδεκα καμώρες
και όλη μέρα το έχτιζαν, τη νύχτα πάλι χαλούσε. [Σπυριδάκης 1939: 409]

Below, by the five rivers, by the five springs, / below, at the ends of the earth, where the world ends, / below, at the ends of the earth, in the middle of the universe, / they were building a bridge and said that it was a fearful one. / It was a bridge they were building, with twelve arches, / and all day they built it, and at night it collapsed again.

If the bridge has a name, then it bears the name of: (a) a geographical object (the city in which it is built, the country, the river);

Σαράντα πέντε μάστοροι κι εξήντα μαθητάδες
Τρεις χρόνους εδουλεύανε στην Άρτας το γεφύρι.
Ολημερίς εκτιζουνε και το βραδυ γκρεμίζεται. [Ευθυμίου 2014: 76]

Forty-five master-builders and sixty apprentices / worked for three years on the bridge of Arta. / All day they build it, and in the evening it collapses.

(b) the chief master;

Σαράντα πέντε μάστοροι κι ως χίλια μαθητούδια
ολημερίτσα δούλων του Παύλου το γιοφύρι,
ολημερίτσα δούλων του βράδ' αργά ξιγέρνει. [Ευθυμίου 2014: 137]

Forty-five masters and as many as a thousand workers / worked all day on Pavlos's bridge, / they worked all day, and late in the evening it gives way.

(c) the metaphorical name Τρίχα (hair).

Ακεί πέραν ‘ς σό Δρακολίμν’, ‘ς ση Τρίχας τό γεφύρι
χίλιοι μαστόρ’ εδούλευαν και μύριοι μαθητάδες. [Ευσταθιάδης 1992: 216-217]

There, beyond, at Drakolimni, at the bridge of Tricha, / a thousand masters and tens of thousands of workers laboured.

2. Complication. The search for a solution to the problem: a solution is found or prompted.

The builders realise that they labour in vain and cannot find a way out. The situation may be aggravated by the arrival of the king's order to execute the master. A decision has to be taken, and the master or masters find it:

2.1. Independently. In this case the need arises to choose a victim, and the choice is made:

- by lot, which falls to the chief master;
- by a pact. Its essence is as follows: whichever wife comes earliest the next morning will be the one walled up. This agreement is always broken by all the participants except one (the youngest), and it is his wife who is to be walled up;
- being alone, the master himself decides to wall up his wife.

2.2. The catalyst of the masters' further behaviour is some being or message from the other world. Thus the need for the sacrifice may be announced:

- by a bird;
- by the voice of a river spirit or of the bridge itself, of a dragon or a stoicheio;
- in a dream;
- by the voice of an archangel or a voice from on high;
- by an unknown voice.

Intermediate between these two categories are the variants in which the decision about the need for a human sacrifice is prompted by an otherworldly being, but the master himself chooses who exactly will become the victim. For example, in the Cypriot variants there may be a choice, when not the wife but one of the relatives may be sacrificed, and then the master's cynical reasoning (κυνικός υπολογισμός) follows, and he chooses precisely the wife, since the ties of blood are dearer to him than those of marriage.

The husband's reaction to the fact that his wife must be walled into the foundation may be:

- negative (in this case the husband of the future victim tries in every way to prevent or delay her death);
- neutral (without hesitation or regret the husband performs the necessary actions).

3. The main part. Actions directed at solving the problem.

In the CSB this structural component can be divided into three scenes.

Scene 1. “Own” territory. It is determined who is to become the construction sacrifice. The victim is on her own territory (at home), and she must come to the place of her death. Her path from home to the place of death resembles the way into the kingdom of the dead. In the Greek variants, unlike,

for example, the Bulgarian, this transition is less clearly visible, since the victim's road from her path to the place of building is not described in detail. They send for her:

- a servant or a boy;
- a bird (the same one that was the messenger, or another, it is unknown);
- the builder himself comes for her;
- she arrives with the meal at an untimely hour;
- the messenger is unknown, the delivery of the message is expressed by an impersonal construction.

The victim receives the information:

- deliberately altered by the intermediary;
- wrongly heard by the intermediary (variants from the Dodecanese islands);
- correct (the husband honestly tells his wife what is to happen; before her death he asks her to feed the child and put it to bed, and she takes leave of the neighbour women).

Scene 2. The path of the victim: the crossing from “own” territory to “alien” territory. In the Balkan CSBs the victim's path from home to the place of building resembles a crossing from the world of the living into the kingdom of the dead. The wife's path from home to the place of her death is transitional, and in the Greek variants she meets on it harbingers of her death:

2.1. The victim's clothing:

- remains unchanged (the future victim asks the messenger with what he has come, with good or with evil, so that she can dress accordingly, and receives the answer that she need not change her clothes, and so she understands that she is summoned for no good);
- black, signifying mourning;
- beautiful (sensing death, the victim puts on her finest attire).

2.2. Forebodings. In some variants the heroine has a presentiment of what is to come, puts the child to sleep and takes leave of the neighbour women.

2.3. The words of the bird: “πίσω δε θα γυρίσης!” (“you will not return!”).

Scene 3. The deception. Having come to the place where she is to die, the victim meets one or two more harbingers of misfortune. The heroine greets the masters and asks why her husband is sad. She is told that the reason is that the master dropped his wedding ring (the loss of the wedding ring is a harbinger of misfortune) into the foundation, and there is no one to fetch it. The heroine is ready to fetch the ring so that her husband should not grieve. Having jumped into the foundation, the woman either finds nothing there, or meets another harbinger of approaching death: she finds a coil of venomous snakes or the severed heads of people. The scene with the ring is plot-forming: by deceit the woman is lured into the foundation.

4. Climax. The elimination of the problem: the making of the construction sacrifice.

The masters wall up either the woman or her shadow, which in this case acts as a substitute for her soul. The second action is connected, as was said above, with the belief that a person's soul resides in their shadow. Understanding that she is being walled up, the woman uses the following objections:

- she has left the house open, the key in the door;

- she has left bread in the oven, linen in the wash;
- she has left the child in the cradle, and so on.

The builders always reject her objections, saying that others will take care of all the unfinished tasks. The victim then tells of two sisters whom the same fate befell as befell her. It is worth noting the wide geography of the buildings spoken of in the different variants: among them one may find practically all the regions of Greece and of the neighbouring countries. An inseparable part of the climax in the Greek variants is the curse that the woman lays in despair upon the building and the master:

- she wishes the bridge to tremble;
- the bridge to roar;
- passers-by to fall from it, as the hairs fall from her head;
- she curses the master's lineage, and so on.

Often the ballad ends here. In many variants, however, there is a denouement.

5. Denouement. The lifting of the curse.

The woman is asked to replace the curse with another, and she does so for the sake of:

- a brother who is to return from a foreign land;
- a son.

6. Ending.

In most variants the ending is absent. The exceptions are certain variants from the Dodecanese, the Cyclades, Euboea, Crete and Cyprus. The ending in the Greek variants takes the form of:

- an address to the child;
- an address to plants and animals.

Thus the plot of the construction-sacrifice ballad fits Propp's formula (lack and the liquidation of lack) [Propp 1969: 195]. The lack in this case is the building that the master or masters need. The liquidation of the lack is carried out by means of the construction sacrifice. One cannot fail to note the presence of oppositions in the plot of the ballad:

- Lack / liquidation of lack;
- Search for a solution to the problem / a solution is found or prompted;
- The brothers' agreement / the breaking of the agreement;
- Obstacles on the victim's path / the obstacles overcome;
- Objections / the rejection of the objections;
- An evil curse / the replacement of the curse by a good one.

In this form the singer keeps it in his head. A more experienced singer will include here more episodes and details, will add all the motifs known to him and use more formulas, while a less experienced one, keeping this scheme in mind, will simply lay out the essence.

The Motif Structure of the Construction-Sacrifice Ballad

Besides the constant elements, the “core”, the list of scenes, the plot without which the building of the construction-sacrifice ballad is impossible, there are also present in it optional components, the motifs, which possess semantic significance. It is precisely they that may help to determine the

place where the ballad arose. Below we examine the main motifs that can be identified in the structure of the construction-sacrifice ballad. The motifs are identified on the basis of the variants studied in this work; the list of motifs is not final. It may be supplemented and altered. We identify motifs on the basis of the following criteria:

1. It possesses semantic significance, while being part of the plot.
2. It is connected with the ancient archetypal or mythological world-view of the people.
3. It can be described predicatively.
4. It is regularly repeated in other ballads, myths or tales.

In the construction-sacrifice ballads the following motifs can be identified:

1. The motif of the auspicious beginning.

This motif is invariant for all variants of the CSB; it is connected with the archetypal world-view. “In erecting a new building a person intrudes into the domain of a being of the Other world. This is perceived by the representatives of the Other world as proud presumption, which is not permitted to a human being. In order to reconcile himself with the powers of the Other world, he must offer a sacrifice. Folk traditions tell of supernatural spirits who govern the building and the stability of walls; here belong also the myths of the building of the walls of Jericho, of the city of Thebes, or of the foundations of Rome” [Schubert 2015: 321-334].

2. The motif of brotherly love.

The motif of brotherly love we identify only in the Greek variants. For the love of a brother who is in a foreign land and must pass over the bridge in whose foundation his sister lies, the victim renounces her curse. In the Greek text the woman who plays the role of the construction sacrifice curses the bridge in indignation, wishing it to collapse, but she is reminded of her dear brother who is in a foreign land, and then she changes her curse. In the history of Greek literature one may find many examples of sisterly love (the love of Electra for Orestes and others).

3. The motif of the brother's return from a foreign land.

The brother is soon to return from a foreign land and to pass over the bridge, and in connection with this the victim cancels her curse. The foreign land is a widespread motif in folk songs, usually representing a trial. The brother for whose sake the woman changes the curse is himself a victim of fate, since he is in a foreign land.

4. The motif of Icarus.

The masters decide to jump from the roof, having fashioned wooden wings from boards, but they fall and are dashed to death. This motif occurs only in the Romanian variants. Here too we see an echo of Cretan mythology. Like Icarus, who flew too close to the sun and fell into the salt sea, the masters are dashed against the ground.

5. The motif of submission to “elders”.

This motif occurs in the Albanian variants of the CSB. By “elder” may be understood not only one's own father or mother, but anyone who is older. It is precisely an elder (in one of the versions a saint, who may also be considered an “elder”, more experienced spiritually) who prompts the Albanian builders to wall up the wife, which they do. In the Albanian variants the mother-in-law, that is, the second mother, orders the daughter-in-law to carry food to her husband, promising to sit with the child in the meantime. The daughter-in-law does not want to go, but she cannot disobey the mother.

6. The motif of the search for “stable” names.

The vila advises finding twins with “stable” names and walling them into the foundation so that the building should stop collapsing. In the variants of the ballad from Serbia the twins are never found, and the vila proposes another solution. In the variant from Bosnia and Herzegovina the twins are successfully found and walled into the wall.

7. The motif of submission to fate.

Having learned from her husband's lips that she is to be walled up, the woman accepts her fate with pride. The motif is characteristic of the Albanian variants of the CSB. She does not argue but accepts her lot with joy. She has already fulfilled her duty, has borne a son, and now her task is to see that her child fares well.

8. The motif of the message from the otherworld.

The builders are long unable to find a way out of the situation, and the solution is prompted to them by a being from the otherworld. In all the Greek variants the main catalyst of the behaviour of the masters who build the bridge is the message received from the otherworld: in order for the bridge to stop collapsing, a sacrifice is needed. The messenger may be a bird that speaks with a human voice, a dragon, a vila or another supernatural being (στοιχειό) [Klimova 2006: 114-130].

In the Bulgarian and Hungarian versions of the ballad the motif of the message from the otherworld is absent, since the decision to wall up the wife is taken by the builders themselves. This points to a loss of the ballad's connection with the supernatural forces.

Труица брата каул сториха:
- Чиято любя най-рано дойдя,
та ми дунясе рана прогимка,
да го вградимя в Бялана града! [Арнаудов 1920: 81]

Three brothers made a pact: / whoever's wife comes earliest / and brings the early meal, / her we shall wall up in the white city!

9. The motif of betrayal.

The youngest brother or the youngest builder turns out to be the only one who does not tell his wife of the pact and keeps his promise. This motif is present in a large number of Bulgarian, Macedonian, Serbian and Greek CSBs. The elder brothers or masters always turn out to be more experienced and cunning, the youngest honest and kind-hearted. This motif is widespread in many tales, both foreign and Russian (for example, Ivan the Fool, the famous character of many Russian tales).

10. The motif of the pursuit of the murderer.

After the murder of the wife, the husband is pursued by her voice. Here an echo of the ancient Greek plot of Orestes's murder of his mother Clytemnestra and his subsequent pursuit by the implacable goddesses of vengeance, the Erinyes (who pursued only the murderers of blood relatives), is evident. As Orestes killed his mother in fulfilment of the will of the god Apollo, so the Romanian master Manole walled up his wife, having heard a heavenly voice in a dream. But neither of them succeeds in escaping pursuit. Orestes, after long wanderings, is saved by Apollo and Athena, while Manole perishes, jumping from the roof. In the Hungarian variants the husband who walled up his wife is tormented by conscience.

11. The motif of the curse.

In the Greek variants of the ballad, unlike the Balkan-Slavic ones, the victim, understanding what fate awaits her, curses the building. Before this she speaks of the fate of her two sisters, whom the same fate befell as befell her.

Πως τρέχουν τα ματάκια μου, να τρέχει το ποτάμι,
ως τρέμει η καρδίτσα μου, να τρέμει το γιοφύρι,
ως πέφτουν τα μαλλάκια μου, να πέφτουν οι διαβάτες. [Ευθυμίου 2014: 96]

As the tears run from my eyes, let the river run; / as my heart trembles, let the bridge tremble; / as the hairs fall from my head, let the passers-by fall.

12. The motif of the separation of mother and child.

The inseparable bond between mother and child continues to exist even after the death of one of them. In Balkan folklore the motif of the separation of child and mother is often used. In the Serbian and Albanian variants this motif is much better developed. The woman asks that little windows be left for her, so that she may feed the child, look at it, rock its cradle with her foot, and so on. In the variant from Bosnia and Herzegovina the mother dies together with the child, and both of them are laid into the foundation of the minaret. In the Hungarian variants the child dies in the night, not surviving the separation from the mother. In the variants from Romania a pregnant woman is walled up, that is, the child perishes together with her in the womb.

13. The motif of union with nature.

After a death that comes about in an unnatural (violent) way, the person is transformed into a part of nature (a plant or a spring). This motif echoes several myths. Thus a parallel with the myth of Narcissus, who after death was turned into a beautiful plant, is visible here. In some Greek variants the walled-up woman too becomes a part of nature; she speaks with the plants.

14. The motif of the spousal sacrifice.

When the master has a choice of whom to sacrifice, he chooses precisely the wife, since she is not a blood relative of his. The master refuses to sacrifice his father, his mother or one of his brothers or sisters, because he will never have others, but resolves to sacrifice his wife, because later he will be able to find another. His drama echoes the drama of Abraham, who was to sacrifice his only child in obedience to the command of the Lord, and the drama of Agamemnon, likewise compelled by an order from on high to sacrifice his daughter Iphigenia. The walling up of the victim happens hastily (the speed is conveyed by a large number of verbs of dramatic character: *πιχάει, παίρνει, ρίχνει*), and it is precisely the chief master who lays the great stone, *ρίχνει μέγα λίθο*.

15. The motif of the three sisters.

When she is walled into the bridge, the woman tells of her two sisters who perished in exactly the same way. This lament, on the one hand, speaks of the significance for the unfolding of the elements of the ballad of the number three, which is seen also in the motif of the three sisters; on the other, it may be used to characterise the building rites in Greece.

16. The motif of the loss of the marriage symbol.

In order to lure his wife into the foundation, the master says that he has dropped there his wedding ring, a precious signet ring or a golden apple. This motif is absent in the Hungarian and Romanian variants. In them another trap is used for the victim: they begin in jest to wall the woman up. This motif is also not used in the Albanian variants: there the husband tells his wife of her fate directly. The wedding ring is considered the most sacred symbol of marriage, of conjugal fidelity and love, and its loss is considered a very bad omen. In the Bulgarian variants the husband too speaks to the

wife of a lost ring, but this ring is not a wedding ring but simply a precious signet, playing rather the role of a costly ornament (a silver signet with a red stone, a golden signet, a silver ring).

ам си изтървах пръстен маламен
 долу в калето, в дълбочините,
 в дребни камъни, дребни молози. [Арnaudов 1920: 81]

I dropped a golden ring / down into the fortress, into the depths, / among the small stones, the small rubble.

In the Serbian variants the husband says that he dropped a golden apple into the foundation.

Ал' говори Мрњавчевић Гојко:
 “Зло је моја вијернице љубо!
 Имао сам од злата јабуку,
 Па ми данас паде у Бојану,
 Те је жалим, прегорет' не могу!” [Карацић 1823: 10-20]

But Mrnjavcevic Gojko says: / “Woe is me, my faithful love! / I had an apple of gold, / and today it fell into the Bojana. / I grieve for it, I cannot get over it!”

17. The motif of the killing of the builders.

The king sees a magnificent temple and orders that the builders who created it be blinded or killed, so that they should not be able to build anything similar. This motif echoes the mythological plot of the building of the labyrinth of the Minotaur by Daedalus. After the labyrinth is built, Daedalus together with his son Icarus is shut up in this same labyrinth, from which they escape with the help of wings.

The presence or absence of the motifs we have worked out in the Balkan CSBs may be reflected in a table. As the table shows, the most motifs (12) are found precisely in the Greek ballad. In second place by number of motifs (8) stands the Romanian ballad, in third (7) the Romani. The Greek ballad, moreover, has the clearest logical sequence of motifs.

Tradition / motif	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
Greek	+	+	+					+	+		+		+	+	+	+	
Albanian	+				+		+					+					
Aromanian	+							+				+			+		
Bulgarian	+								+								+
Bosnian	+					+		+				+					
Hungarian	+									+		+					
Macedonian	+								+								
Pomak	+											+					
Romanian	+			+				+		+		+	+				+
Serbo-Croatian	+					+			+			+					+
Turkish	+							+									
Romani	+							+									

[Original table preserved from the Russian version. The grid follows the motif attributions stated explicitly in the paper; the original markings should be verified against the Russian source. Manual formatting required.]

Conclusion

Having studied the Greek plot of the bridge of Arta against the Balkan background, the following conclusions may be drawn:

The basis of the plot conflict is the walling up of the wife of the chief master in the foundation of the building, in order to offer a sacrifice so that it should stop collapsing, the motif of the “auspicious beginning”, that is, of the human sacrifice made so that the building should begin to “live”. The following scheme will be invariant for all the versions of the Balkans:

5. Exposition. The unsuccessful building.
6. Complication. The problem and the search for a solution. A solution is found or prompted.
7. The development of events. Actions directed at eliminating the problem.
 - The summoning of the victim to the place of death.
 - The path of the victim from home to the place of death. On this path the victim may meet: harbingers of death; natural cataclysms; difficult tasks. The woman comes to the place of her death in spite of everything.
 - The place of death.
8. Climax. The sacrifice. The elimination of the problem. The human sacrifice must be valuable. One of the following variants is possible: the wife of the builder; the child of the builder; twins with “stable” names, who are difficult to find (the search takes many years).
- (5. Denouement. The victim is reconciled to her lot.) (6. Ending. What happens after a time.)

Components 5 and 6 are not structure-forming and may be absent.

In the Balkan construction-sacrifice ballads we have identified the following motifs (in alphabetical order in the Russian original):

9. The motif of the auspicious beginning.
10. The motif of brotherly love.
11. The motif of the brother's return from a foreign land.
12. The motif of Icarus.
13. The motif of submission to parents.
14. The motif of the search for “stable” names.
15. The motif of submission to fate.
16. The motif of the message from the otherworld.
17. The motif of the betrayal of the younger brother.
18. The motif of the pursuit of the murderer.
19. The motif of the curse.
20. The motif of the separation of mother and child.
21. The motif of union with nature.
22. The motif of the spousal sacrifice.
23. The motif of the three sisters.
24. The motif of the loss of the marriage symbol.
25. The motif of the killing of the builders.

The main structural features of the Greek ballad are the motifs of:

- the message from the otherworld (absent in the Bulgarian, Hungarian and Macedonian variants);
- the loss of the marriage symbol or precious ornament;
- brotherly love (only in the Greek variants);
- the curse (only in the Greek variants);
- the three sisters (only in the Aromanian and Greek variants);
- the spousal sacrifice (only in the Greek variants).

The most motifs are found in the Greek ballad. The Greek ballad, moreover, has the clearest logical sequence of motifs (for example, the motif of the curse is followed by the lifting of the curse). At the same time the Romanian ballad undoubtedly has a very ancient origin, as is indicated by the motif of Icarus, the motif of the pursuit of the murderer, the motif of union with nature and the motif of the killing of the builders.

The question of the origin of the CSB in the Balkans remains open to this day. In our opinion, it is of Greek origin, because it:

26. is the most widely current;
27. has a clear sequence of motifs, unlike the other ballads;
28. has an archaic archetypal structure, unlike the sentimental literary working out of the motifs in the Serbian, Hungarian and Aromanian ballads.

It is interesting to observe the transformations of the Greek plot across the Balkans. Having studied the plots of the other Balkan construction-sacrifice ballads, we identified the following features:

Distinctive features of the Albanian variants:

29. The type of building: a fortress, not a bridge.
30. In one of the three variants we examine it is said that the builders were Orthodox, and this is emphasised several times.
31. Information about the need for the construction sacrifice comes to the masters in the form of the advice of some wise person (a saint or an elder).
32. The wife of the builder is sent to the place of death by the mother-in-law, in spite of her objections.
33. The scene of deception is absent.
34. The woman accepts her lot with pride and blesses the building; her last words are filled with joy that her son will become here the lawful master.
35. The woman asks that openings be left in the wall, so that she may feed and lull her son.
36. In one of the variants the victim sees a dream on the eve of her death, a harbinger of the death to come.

Distinctive features of the Aromanian ballad:

37. The beginning of the Aromanian ballad is much more detailed than that of the Greek. In the complication of the Aromanian ballad *Puntea din Arta* the story is told of how the masters lived in their native city of Nanta, and why precisely they were chosen for the building of the bridge of Arta (the motivation). The builders set the king three conditions: their wives with the children will move to them; the patron will pay all their expenses; to build the

bridge they need seven years. The king agrees, but in case of deception he threatens to slaughter the builders. The building begins, but for six years the building collapses. The masters gather in council, but cannot find a solution.

38. The motif of the separation of mother and child is more strongly worked out and very sentimental: the builders are to leave the woman's breasts free, so that she can feed little Constantine, otherwise he will die of hunger, but they refused to do this.
39. It contains the scene with the three sisters. There are many motifs similar to the Greek ones (most likely this is connected with the fact that the variant of the Aromanian ballad we examine was recorded on the territory of Greece).

Structural features of the Bulgarian ballad:

40. The type of building is unstable. Thus the master (he is almost always called Manole) may build a bridge, a monastery, a city or a fortress. From this it follows that the bridge as a symbol of the crossing from one world into another loses its significance in the Bulgarian variants.
41. The decision about the construction sacrifice is always taken by the masters themselves.
42. A scene of the pact is present.
43. Natural cataclysms act as obstacles.
44. A scene with the loss of the ring is present.

The ballads of Bosnia and Herzegovina differ from the Greek ones in that:

45. Children act in the role of the construction sacrifice. Thus, in the first variant we examine a dervish-pasha, in building a minaret, walls up his own younger son. In this case he has a choice and consults his wife, but, having met with a rebuff from her, makes the choice himself. In another variant we examine, by order of the vila, the builder finds twins with "stable" names, Stoja and Ostoja, and lays them into the foundation of the building.
46. The need for the sacrifice is announced to the master: in a dream; by a vila.

The Hungarian ballad has the following distinctive features:

47. In it the decision about the construction sacrifice is taken independently.
48. The obstacles on the victim's path are natural cataclysms.
49. The victim is allowed to go home and take leave of the child and friends.
50. The ending: the little son searches everywhere for his mother. In the end he learns what has happened and dies.

The Macedonian ballad does not differ in structure from the Bulgarian; the same scenes are present in it. The Macedonian ballads, however, are less detailed than the Bulgarian. The type of building is likewise unstable. The Pomak ballads, recorded in Xanthi, are also very similar to the Bulgarian. In the Pomak variant the name of the victim is Yurka Kadona. The only feature distinguishing them from all the rest is that after the victim's death her child will be raised by her mother.

The Romanian ballad has the following features:

51. The development of events in the Romanian ballad is preceded by a long prehistory.
52. A voice from heaven, heard in a dream, is the catalyst of the masters' actions.
53. Natural cataclysms, wind and rain, become the obstacles on the victim's path to the place of death.
54. The wife is told that they wish to wall her up in jest, and they wall her up in earnest.

55. The ending, which refers at once to several ancient Greek myths.

Structural features of the Serbo-Croatian CSB:

56. Very long introductory motifs.

57. The search for twins with “stable” names.

58. An ending with the words that to this day women who have no milk in their breasts come to be healed at the place where the girl was walled up.

The Turkish ballad resembles a retelling of the Greek CSB. The structure of the Romani ballad differs from that of the Greek in the following:

59. The ballad has long introductory motifs.

60. A regret that the brothers have no parents able to give sensible advice.

61. The victim knows in advance of her coming death (likewise from a prophetic dream), but comes all the same, despite having a child only three days old.

62. The master himself ends up in the foundation and asks his wife to pull him out.

The most similar to the Greek ballad in structure is the Aromanian ballad. The one that differs most from it (as from the others) is the Romanian ballad.

We mapped two elements:

63. The catalyst of the masters' behaviour (see Appendix 2.1). This may be a bird, a vila, a stoicheio or another spirit, the masters themselves, an unknown voice, a voice from on high, a prophetic dream, the advice of a wise man. As the map shows, the Bulgarian, Macedonian and Hungarian ballads have lost their connection with the supernatural forces: in them the decision is taken by the masters themselves. In the Albanian ballads responsibility for the decision rests with a wise man or an old man, that is, for the inhabitants of Albania it is important to heed the advice of elders. In Greece the motif of the transmission of the message from the otherworld by a bird is widespread. This is connected with the belief that birds can move between worlds.

64. The type of building (see Appendix 2.2). The map shows that in the ballads of the Balkans the building is either a city or fortress (the city as the cosmogonic imago mundi, the sacred axis of the universe), or a monastery (the search for a holy beginning in life, the monastery as a representation of paradise, the heavenly Jerusalem). In Greece a bridge is always used as the building (the crossing between worlds, the crossing of boundaries, the taming of the elements, of the destructive force of nature).

Thus the area of distribution of the CSB in the Balkans may be divided into two macro-regions (according to the plot):

65. the Hungarian-Romanian-South Slavic-Albanian zone in the northern Balkan region, where a city or a monastery, Arges (or the fortresses of Deva and Skadar), is built;

66. the Mediterranean Greek-South Slavic-Aromanian zone, stretching from the Ionian Sea to Asia Minor and Cyprus.

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Appendix

1. List of used versions of the ballad about the construction sacrifice¹.

1. 1. Greek versions (GV)

Number	Exact place of recording	Song title or first lines	Source
1.	Epirus	«Χίλιοι μαστόροι δούλευαν 'ς της Άρτας το γιοφύρι»	Ζωγράφειος Αγών, Μνημεία της ελληνικής αρχαιότητας Τ. 1, 1891. Σ. 82.
2.	Arta, Epirus	«Χίλιοι τριακόσιοι μάστοροι κ' εξήντα μαθητούδια»	Σεραφεΐμ του Βυζαντίου «Δοκίμιον ιστορικής τινος περιλήψεως τής ποτε αρχαίας και εγκρίτου Ηπειρωτικής πόλεως Άρτης και της οσαύτως νεωτέρας πόλεως Πρεβέζης», Αθήνα, 1884 Σ. 381.

¹ We provide the title or first lines of each song, the edition in which it was published, the year of publication, and the exact place of recording, if specified in the collection itself.

3.	Epirus		<i>«Η αστερέωτος γέφυρα της Άρτης»</i>	Λαογραφικό αρχείο. 322. 1881 Σ. 20.
4.	Plesivica,	Epirus	<i>«Το γεφύρι της Τρίχας ή Άρτας»</i>	Λαογραφικό αρχείο. 393. 1885. Σ. 29
5.	Aidochori,	Serres,	<i>«Σαράντα μαστορόπουλα κι εξήντα δυο μάστοροι»</i>	Αικατερινίδης Γ. ΚΛ χ/φο αρ. 2779, αρ. ταιν. 600, 1963.
6.	Melenikitsi,	Serres,	<i>«Σαράντα πέντε μάστοροι κι εξήντα δυο καρφάδες»</i>	Αικατερινίδης Γ. ΚΛ χ/φο αρ. 2779, αρ. ταιν. 605, 1963.
7.	Sisamya,	Serres,	<i>«Οι τετρακόσιοι μάστοροι, τα χίλια μαστορούδια»</i>	Αικατερινίδης Γ. ΚΛ χ/φο αρ. 2779, αρ. ταιν. 609, 1963.
8.	Nikoklia,	Serres,	<i>«Σαράντα μαστορόπουλα κι εξήντα δυο μάστοροι»</i>	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη, Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 6.
9.	Kavakli,	Karies,	<i>«Το γεφύρι της Γεώργαινας»</i>	Λουλουδόπουλος Μ. Ανέκδοτος συλλογή Καρυών Καβακλή, Βάρνη, 1903. Σ. 65-66.
10.	Enos,	Thrace	<i>«Η κυρά Βδοκιά»</i>	Ο εν Κ/πόλει Ελλην. Φιλολογικός Σύλλογος, Ζώντα μνημεία. Τ. 9, 1875. Σ. 359.
11.	Sterna,	Evros,	<i>«Σαράντα πέντε μάστοροι κι ως χίλια μαθητούδια»</i>	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη, Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 137.
12.	Kessani,	Thrace	<i>«Του κάλφα το τραγούδι»</i>	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο. 176, 1889. Σ. 77.
13.	Megara,	Central Greece	<i>«Της Άρτας το γιοφύρι»</i>	ΛΑΟΓΡΑΦΙΑ. XVIII. Αθήνα, 1959. Σ. 522
14.	Eurytania,	Central Greece	<i>«Η στοιχειωμένη γύνη μετά των δύο αυτής αδελφών»</i>	Ιατρίδης Α. Συλλογή δημοτικών ασμάτων, Αθήνα, 1859. Σ 28-30.
15.	Arachova,	Central Greece	<i>«Ο στοιχειωμένος άνθρωπος επί τινι βρύσει της εν Παρνασσώ κομποπόλεως»</i>	Ιατρίδης Α. Συλλογή δημοτικών ασμάτων, Αθήνα, 1859. Σ. 93-94.
16.	Lidoriki,	Central Greece	<i>« Το τραγούδι του γεφυριού της Άρτας»</i>	Λαογραφικό αρχείο №1235, 1875. Σ. 22-30.

17.	Omohori, Larisa, Thessaly	« <i>Εννιά μάστοροι το χτιζαν τ'ς Άτανας γιοφύρι</i> » ²	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη, Τ. 2, 2014. Σ.358-360.
18.	Omohori, Larisa, Thessaly	« <i>Εννιά μάστοροι το χτιναν σ'ην Άδανα γιοφύρι</i> »	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη, Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 362-367.
19.	Karditsa, Thessaly	« <i>Σαράντα πέντε μάστοροι, εξήντα δύο καλφάδες</i> »	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο № 969, 1929. Σ. 499-502.
20.	Agios Georgios, Thessaly	« <i>Το γιοφύρι της Άρτας</i> »	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο № 2401, 1961. Σ. 7-8.
21.	Euboea	« <i>Της Άρτας το γιοφύρι</i> »	Σέττας Χ. Δ. Εύβοια. Λαϊκός Πολιτισμός - Δημοτικά τραγούδια, Επωδές, παραδόσεις, αινίγματα, παροιμίες, λαϊκή τέχνη. \ 1976. Τ. 3. Σ. 98.
22.	Skiathos	« <i>Κάτω στην ά- κάτω στην ά- κάτω στην άκρη του γιαλού</i> »	Δόμνα Σαμίου [Электронный ресурс]. Режим доступа: 1975.
23.	Avlonari, Euboea	« <i>Η καμάρα</i> »	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο № 1088, 1905. Σ. 55.
24.	Aliveri, Euboea	« <i>Σαράντα πέντε μάστοροι κι εξήντα μαθητάδες</i> »	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη. Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 76-79.
25.	Corinthia, Peloponnese	« <i>Εξήντα πέντε μάστοροι κ' εξήντα δύο καλφάδες</i> »	Λελέκος Μ Επιδόρπιον.. Αθήνα, 1888, Τ. 2. Σ. 216-217.
26.	Corinthia, Peloponnese	« <i>Σαράντα μαστορόπουλα κ' εξήντα δύο μαστόροι</i> »	Λελέκος Μ Επιδόρπιον. Αθήνα, 1888, Τ. 2. Σ. 217-218.
27.	Sparta, Peloponnese	« <i>Το στοίχειωμα του γεφυριού</i> »	Λαογραφικό αρχείο 1091B, 1914 Σ. 3.
28.	Methoni, Peloponnese	« <i>Το γεφύρι της Άρτας</i> »	Ταρσούλη Γ. Μωραίτικα τραγούδια Κορώνης – Μεθόνης, Αθήνα, 1944.. Σ. 87.

² The song was performed by an emigrant from Cappadocia

29.	Corfu	«Σαράντα πέντε μάστοροι κι εξήντα μαθητάδες»	Πολίτης Ν.Γ. Εκλογαί από τα δημοτικά τραγούδια του ελληνικού λαού, Αθήνα, 1914. Σ. 131-133.
30.	Corfu	«Η γέφυρα της Άρτας»	Passow A. Popularia carmina Graeciae recentioris. Τραγούδια ρωμαίικα, Lipsiae, 1842. Σ. 388-390.
31.	Kefalonia	«Η γέφυρα της Άρτας»	Passow A. Popularia carmina Graeciae recentioris. Τραγούδια ρωμαίικα, Lipsiae, 1842. Σ. 390-391.
32.	Corfu	«Της Τρίχας το γιοφύρι»	Μαρτζούκου Γιάννης, Κερκυραϊκά τραγούδια, Αθήνα, 1959. Σ. 85.
33.	Antimachia, Kos	«Το γεφύρι της Αντιμάχειας»	Dieterich K. Sprache und Volksüberlieferungen der südl. Sporaden, Wien, 1908. S. 291-293
34.	Olympus, Karpathos	«Γιοφύρι θεμελιώνουσι στις Άρτας το μποδάσι»	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη. Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 423-426.
35.	Kos	«Το στοιχειωμένο γεφύρι»	Ταρσούλη Α. Δωδεκάνησα, Τ. 3., 1950. Σ. 116-117.
36.	Nisyros	«Το στοιχειωμένο γιοφύρι»	Kazawis G. Νισήρου λαογραφικά, New York, 1940. S. 26-27.
37.	Amorgos	«Της Αρτάς το γιοφύρι»	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο № 1684 Α, 1857. Σ. 49 .
38.	Tinos, Arnades	«Της Τρίχας το γεφύρι»	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο № 1400, 1895. Σ. 3.
39.	Tinos, Arnades	«Της Τρίχας το γιοφύρι»	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο № 1402, 1895. Σ. 111.
40.	Tinos, Falatades	«Της Άρτας το γιοφύρι»	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο № 1400, 1895. Σ. 27.
41.	Crete	«Η γυναίκα του πρωτομάστορα»	Jeannarakis A. Άσματα Κρητικά, Leipzig, 1876. S. 209-210.
42.	Hamezi, Crete	« Η γυναίκα του πρωτομάστορα»	Παπαδάκη Ε. Λόγια του Στειακού λαού, Αθήνα, 1938. Σ. 6
43.	Vyannos, Crete	« Η καμάρα του Ρεθέμνου»	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο № 249, 1906. Σ. 2
44.	Rogdia, Crete	« Η καμάρα»	Ζωγράφειος Αγών, Μνημεία της ελληνικής

			αρχαιότητος Τ. 1, 1891. Σ. 75-76.
45.	Akdag, Cappadocia, Turkey	«Της Τρίχας το γεφύρι»	Lagarde P. Neusgriechisches aus Klein- Asien, Gottingen, 1887. S. 39.
46.	Malakopi, Cappadocia, Turkey	«Ηννιά μαστόρ' το έχτιναν»	Παχτικός Γ. Δημόδη ελληνικά άσματα της Μικράς Ασίας, Αθήνα, 1905. Σ. 29.
47.	Akdag, Cappadocia, Turkey	«Η γέφυρα των Αδάνων»	Lagarde P. Neusgriechisches aus Klein- Asien, Gottingen, 1887. S.40.
48.	Silata, Cappadocia, Turkey	«Το γιοφύρι 'σ την 'Αδανα»	Φαρασόπουλου Σ. Τα σύλατα, 1895. Σ. 107-109.
49.	Kizik, Turkey	Της Τρίχας το γιοφύρι	Λαογραφικό αρχείο Νο 209, 1877. Σ.44.
50.	Oludeniz, Turkey	«Η Λυγινή κι του γιοφύριν».	Λαογραφικό αρχείο Νο2196,1941. Σ. 85-86.
51.	Chios	« Η γυναίκα του πρωτομάστορα»	Αμαντος Κ. « Χιακά Χρονικά», Τ. 1., 1911. Σ. 140-141.
52.	Agia Paraskevi, Lesbos	«Της Κρεμαστής το γεφύρι»	Παρασκευαίδης Χρ. Η παλαιά Αγία Παρασκευή, Mytilena, 1936.Σ. 135.
53.	Trabzon, Turkey	«Της Τρίχας το γεφύρι».	Μελανοφρύδης Π. Η εν Πόντω ελληνική γλώσσα. Batoumi, 1910. Σ. 38.
54.	Trabzon, Turkey	«Της Τρίχας το γεφύρι»	Λαογραφία 9, 1929. Σ. 602-603.
55.	Santa, Turkey	« Της Τρίχας το γεφύρι»	Αθανασσιάδης Ε. Άσματα ποικίλα Σάντας. Αρχείο Πόντου. Τ. 2. Σ. 216-217.
56.	Inepolis, Sinop, Turkey	« Της Τρίχας το γεφύρι»	Αρχείον Πόντου Νο 24, Αθήνα, 1901. Σ. 150-151.
57.	Famagusta, Cyprus	«Το τραούιν της Μαρρρουλλούς»	Λαογραφία 6, 1917. Σ. 600-602.
58.	Paphos, Cyprus	«Της Μαρουλλούς»	Λαογραφικό Αρχείο Νο 1896B, 1953. Σ. 54- 58.
59.	Exo Metohi, Nicosia, Cyprus	«Η Μαρουλλού»	Κυπριανός Σ. Το Παγκύπριον Γυμνάσιον και η Λαογραφία, Λευκοσία, 1958. Σ.101.
60.	Anagio, Cyprus	«Το γιοφύριν της Μαρουλλούς»	Σπυριδάκης Κ. Κυπριακά Γράμματα, Τ.4, Λευκοσία 1939. Σ. 409-410.

1.2. Balkan background (BB)

Number	Exact place of recording	Song title or first lines	Source
1.	Albanian (Tirana, Albania)	«Kënga E Kalasë Së Shkodrës»	Sako Z. Antologjia e folklorit shqiptar. Tirane, 1953. S. 40-41.
2.	Albanian (Albania)	«Песнь о построении Шкодры»	Старинные албанские сказания, М., 1971. С. 161-164.
3.	Albanian (Albania)	«Rozafati»	Skendi S. Albanian and south Slavic oral epic poetry, Philadelphia, 1954. P. 391-398.
4.	Aromanian (Veroia, Central Macedonia, Greece)	«Puntea din Arta»	Papahagi T., Antologie aromănească, București, 1922. S. 67-73.
5.	Bulgarian (Tserovo, Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria)	«Уста Мустафа вгражда невестата си в Будинграда»	Арнаудов М. Вградена невеста. Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 60, София, 1992. С. 353.
6.	Bulgarian (Kozichino village, Pomorie, Bulgaria)	«Майстор Манолчо вгражда невестата си в моста на Тунджа»	Арнаудов М. Вградена невеста. Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 34, София, 1920. С. 351.
7.	Bulgarian (Ustovo, Smolyan, Bulgaria)	«Вградена Невеста»	Арнаудов М. Вградена невеста. Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 34, София, 1920. С. 353.
8.	Bulgarian (Khrabrovo, Provadiysko, Bulgaria)	«Братя дюлгери вграждат невеста в кале на Дунав».	Арнаудов М. Вградена невеста. Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 34, София, 1920. С. 366.
9.	Bulgarian (Gashchevtsi, Veliko Tarnovo, Bulgaria)	«Града градеше Маноил майстор»	Арнаудов М. Вградена невеста. Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 34, София, 1920. С. 366.
10.	Bulgarian (Hursovo, Blagoevgrad,	«Майстор Манаил вгражда невестата си в манастир»	Арнаудов М. Вградена невеста. Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 60, София, 1992. С.

	Bulgaria)		350-351.
11.	Bulgarian (Malko Trnovo, Chirpan, Bulgaria)	«Майстор Павлю прави мост над Марица, Арда и Тунджа и вгражда невястата си»	Арnaudов М. Вградена невеста.- Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 60,София, 1992. С. 360.
12.	Bosnian (Sarajevo city, Bosnia and Herzegovina)	«Zidanje ćuprije u Višegradu»	Hörmann K. Narodne pjesme Bošnjaka I, Bošnačka Književnost u 100 knjiga, Sarajevo, 1889. S. 146-151.
13.	Bosnian (city Mostar, Bosnia and Herzegovina)	«Построение минарета Дервиш-Паши»	Песни южных славян / Сост. Ю. Смирнов. М., 1976. С. 771-776.
14.	Hungarian (Romanian)	«Жена каменщика Келемена»	Трилистник. Стихи советских поэтов// под. ред. П. Антокольского, Е. Винокурова, М. Зенкевича, Н. Любимова, Б. Слуцкого., М., 1971. С.147-149.
15.	Macedonian (Macedonia)	«Сид ми зидае девет мајстори»	Пенушлиски К. Македонски народни балади, -Скопје,1983. С. 86.
16.	Macedonian (Kičevo village, Western Macedonia)	«Зисъ ми зидае деветъ майстори»	Икономовъ В. Сборникъ отъ старо-народни обичаи въ Дебърско и Кичевско (Западна Македония), София, 1893. С. 84-85.
17.	Macedonian (Rogachevo, Tetovo, Macedonia)	«Мост ми сидат девет мајстори»	Арnaudов М. Вградена невеста.- Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 34,София, 1920. С. 344.
18.	Macedonian (Kratovo, Macedonia)	«Мост ми сидат деветмана брака на река Манцева»	Коцевски С.Дервниот град Кратово низ вековите, Скопје, 2003. С. 106.
19.	Macedonian (Karnobat, Bulgaria)	«Суруцан паша прави мост на река Тунца»	Арnaudов М. Вградена невеста.- Сборник за народни умотворения и народопис, 34,София, 1920. С. 360.
20.	Romanian (Cepu village, Galati, Moldova)	«Мастер Маноле»	Памфиле Т. Кынтече де царэ. В., 1913, с. 19—24

21.	Romanian (Romania)	«Monastirea Argesului»	Alecsandri V. Poezii populare ale Românilor. Chiinu, 1998. P. 250-260.
22.	Romanian (Albesti, Romania)	«Zidirea manastirii Argesului»	Mateescu C. N. Balade populare romanesti, Chişinău- Bucureşti, 1997. P. 227-235.
23.	Romanian (Făgăraş, Romania)	«Meşterul Manole»	<i>Ioş I.</i> Balada Meşterului Manole şi variantelele transilvănene. Revista di Folklor, T. 7, Bucureşti, 1962. P. 22-56.
24.	Serbian (Kalaşin, Montenegro)	«Зиданье Скадра»	Караджич В. С Народне српске пјесме., Лейпциг, 1823. Т. 2. С. 10-20.
25.	Serbian (Belgrade, Serbia)	«The building of Scadar»	<i>Noyes G.R. Bacon. L.</i> Heroic Ballads of Serbia. Boston, 1913. P. 15-20.
26.	Pomak (Sminti, Xanthi, Thrace, Greece)	«Trimína brátýe»	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη. Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 182-187.
27.	Pomak (Glavki, Xanthi, Thrace, Greece)	«Trimína brátýe»	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη. Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 189-196.
28.	Turkish (Orestida, Evros, Greece)	«Kirk tane dülger köprü tuturdular»	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη. Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 197-203.
29.	Turkish (Orestida, Evros, Greece)	«Kirk tane dülger köprü tuturdular»	Ευθυμίου Λ. Ο κύκλος τραγουδιών Της Άρτας το γεφύρι. Θεματικός και συστηματικός κατάλογος. Καταγραφές και παραλλαγές, Θεσσαλονίκη. Τ. 2, 2014. Σ. 203-208.
30.	Gypsy	«The Song of the Bridge»	Gilliat-Smith B. A new version of the Song of the Bridge, Journal of Gypsy Lore Society, 4, Edinburgh,

2.1. The motif of the message from the otherworld / the catalyst of the masters' behaviour

2.2. The type of building in the Balkan construction-sacrifice ballads

Translator's Note

This document is an English adaptation of a research paper originally written in Russian and completed earlier at the Department of Byzantine and Modern Greek Philology, Moscow State University. The adaptation stays as close as possible to the original wording, structure and reasoning. No new findings, interpretations or conclusions have been introduced, and the tentative character of the original conclusions has been preserved.